

STATIC AND DYNAMIC THROUGH THICKNESS LAMINA PROPERTIES OF THICK LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Thick laminates are increasingly present in large composites structures such as wind turbine blades. Different factors are suspected to be involved in the decreased static and dynamic performance of thick laminates. These include the effect of self-heating, the scaling effect, and the manufacturing process influence.

The aim of this work is to study the through thickness variation of static and dynamic lamina properties in thick laminates. For this purpose, 60-70 mm thick unidirectional GFRP/epoxy infused panels were divided in sub-laminates with the help of peel-ply layers at different thickness positions. From each sub-laminate, 4 mm thick compression coupons with integrated tabs and tension coupons were manufactured. In order to characterize the manufacturing influence, the 60-70 mm thick laminates plates were monitored during the manufacturing.

Static and fatigue tests were carried out for each sub-laminate in order to study the lamina properties at different thicknesses positions through the thickness. The present work reports temperature profiles and residual stress measurements through the thickness recorded during the manufacturing, as well as experimental data from static and fatigue tests (S-N curves) of sub-laminates obtained at different thickness positions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thick laminates are widely used in wind turbine blades, specifically cap and root sub-components can have thicknesses between 40-60 mm in a 40 meter long blade and up to 100-150mm thicknesses for a 100 meter blade. Generally, blade designs are based on mechanical properties determined by static and fatigue coupon tests of 1-4mm thick laminates. However, a thickness effect has been observed in the limited available experimental data, showing significantly shorter fatigue life in thick laminates.

A decrease on thick laminates final properties has been reported for carbon fiber pre-pregs [1] as well as for glass fiber infused composites [2]. In addition to scaling effects [3] and the self-heating effect [4] during fatigue, it is suspected that thick laminates manufacturing process influence the final properties of thick laminates in comparison with thin laminates.

In order to evaluate laminate performance, a laminate has to be manufactured first. Different variables in the manufacturing process might modify the final properties, such as the curing cycle, the layup alignment tolerances and the infusion process.

White [5] reported that the curing temperature determines the degree of curing and the resin system ultimate strengths. Commonly the curing cycles are divided into two or more temperature steps [6] in order to avoid excessive temperature peaks due to the exothermal curing reaction. While for thin laminates curing temperature through the thickness does not show important gradients, for thick laminates temperatures can vary strongly through the thickness during the curing cycle due to the low thermal conductivities. In addition, temperature gradients during the curing cycle are related to residual stresses in composites which can lead to warpage and shrinkage [7,8].

In order to monitor the curing cycle and the residual stresses different techniques can be used. Thermocouples and dielectric sensors allow to monitor the evolution of the curing temperature and matrix curing degree respectively. Strain gauges and embedded fiber Bragg grating sensors allow to monitor the residual stresses during the curing. Alternatively the hole drilling method (ASTM E837) can be also used in order to determine residual stresses once the part has been manufactured.

White and Kim [9] developed and studied the technique of staged curing, in which two or more thin (<5mm thick) pre-preg laminates are manufactured at once with a similar curing cycle per staged laminate. Moreover, Ciriscioli [10] reported a technique to determine mechanical properties of thick composites laminates manufactured with pre-pregs. Such technique was applied in order to compare the properties between laminates of different thicknesses at the middle thickness position. In addition, there is available literature refereeing to through thickness properties [11,12]. However, in such literature the main focus is related to materials properties related to the 23 and 13 planes.

On account of the limited literature found describing experimentally the lamina properties (plane 12, see figure 1) through the thickness, this experimental work was carried out. Therefore, sub-laminates from GFRP/epoxy infused thick laminates were extracted and subsequently tested in order to answer whether plane 12 lamina properties through the thickness are even or not.

Figure 1: Main laminate orientations. Plane 12, 23 and 31.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental work was done in two stages. The manufacturing process of the thick laminates including the sub-laminates extraction, and the static and fatigue tests of the sub-laminates coupons.

2.1 Manufacturing process

Two plates were vacuum infused with a commonly used wind energy epoxy resin (Hexion RIM135) and a UD glass fibre type E of 600 gr/m² non-crimp fabric. In order to allow the extraction of the sub-laminate plates (see figure 2), alternate peel ply layers with layers of reinforcement fabrics were stacked up. While for the plate A a standard Nylon peel ply with no realising coating was used, for plate B a peel ply with PTFE realising coating was layup.

Six type K thermocouples were embedded at different thickness positions in the laminate in order to monitor the temperatures. In addition, four strain gauges were also embedded in order to monitor the residual stresses during plate A curing cycle (see table 1 and figure 3).

Figure 2: Sub-laminates manufacturing and extraction method. The laminates is cured with peel ply layers in between fabric layers (left). The cured laminate is divided into sub-laminates at peel ply layers locations (right).

	Plate A	Plate B
Thickness [mm]	55.65 mm (80 layers)	64 mm (80 layers)
Layup	5x (10UD PP 4UD PP) 10UD	5x (10UD PP 4UD PP) 10UD
Peel ply type (PP)	Nylon	PTFE
Temperature sensors (T) and strain gauges (S)	T1: layer 1-2 S1, T2: layer 15-16 S2, T3: layer 29-30 S3, T4: layer 45-46 S4, T5: layer 59-60 T6: layer 73-74	T1: layer 1-2 T2: layer 15-16 T3: layer 29-30 T4: layer 45-46 T5: layer 59-60 T6: layer 73-74
Sub-laminates identification	Mold-S1: layer 1-10 S1: layer 11-14 S1-S2: layer 15-24 S2: layer 25-28 S2-S3: layer 29-38 S3: layer 39-42 S3-S4: layer 43-52 S4: layer 53-56 S4-S5: layer 57-66 S5: layer 67-70 S5-S6: layer 71-80	Mold-S1: layer 1-10 S1: layer 11-14 S1-S2: layer 15-24 S2: layer 25-28 S2-S3: layer 29-38 S3: layer 39-42 S3-S4: layer 43-52 S4: layer 53-56 S4-S5: layer 57-66 S5: layer 67-70 S5-S6: layer 71-80
Curing cycle	Infusion: 25°C Soak 1: 35°C – 380min Soak 2: 80°C – 800min	Infusion: 25°C Soak 1: 35°C – 380min Soak 2: 80°C – 800min

Table 1: Plates manufacturing parameters and layout

	Plate A	Plate B
Static compression test (0°)*	Mold-S1, S1-S2, S2-S3 S3-S4, S4-S5, S5-S6 (damaged)	Mold-S1, S1-S2, S2-S3 S3-S4, S4-S5, S5-S6
Static tension test (0°)*	-	S1, S2, S3, S4, S5
Fatigue compression test (0°)**	-	Mold-S1, S2-S3, S5-S6
Fatigue tension test (0°)**	-	S1, S3, S5

*Static tests, 6 coupons per sublaminates

**Fatigue tests, 10-15 coupons per sublaminates

Table 2: Test matrix

Figure 3: Photo of plate A. Detail of the thermocouple and strain gauge.

Figure 4: Tension (top) and compression coupons (bottom) example.

The infusions were carried out at 0.9 bars pressure differential between vacuum port and resing supply line and mould and resin temperatures of 25°C. The infusion times were 25-30 minutes long. The mixing ratios of the resin (Hexion RIM135) and hardener (Hexion RIM137) was as the ones prescribed by the manufacturer, i.e. 100:30. The mould was setup to follow the same curing cycles for plate A and B, with two temperature stages. Initially the laminate was heated up to 35°C for 380 minutes until the curing reaction finished. In a second stage a post-curing cycle was applied at 80°C for 800 minutes. Finally, the plates were released from the mould and subdivided into sub-laminates where the peel ply layers were located.

2.2 Mechanical tests setup

Static and fatigue tests were performed on sub-laminates under both tension and compression. For the compression tests, coupons with 4 mm gauge section thickness were used. The compression coupons were tested on a MTS servo hydraulic 100kN test frame. Static tests were performed with a CLC fixture according to ASTM D6641 and fatigue tests were performed with the standard machine clamping system. Compression coupons were manufactured from sub-laminates from plate A and B according to the test matrix of table 2. The compression coupon geometry corresponds with a gauge section milled geometry with integrated tabs [2] (see figure 4). Static tests were carried out at a test speed of 1 mm/min and fatigue tests at frequencies of 2 Hz.

Tension coupons according ISO 527-5/A 2.5mm thick and 15mm wide were manufactured from plate B sub-laminates according to the test matrix of table 2. Static tests of tension coupons were carried out in a Zwick 100kN tests frame at a test speed of 1mm/min. In addition fatigue tests of tension coupons were carried out at tests frequencies of 2Hz.

Figure 5: Measurements from strain gauges embedded in plate A (left) and thermocouples embedded in plate A (right).

Figure 6: Measurements from thermocouples embedded in plate B (left), and temperature profile through the thickness at maximum curing cycle temperature in plate B (right).

Figure 7: DSC glass transition temperatures (T_{g2}) and fiber weight ratios through the thickness. Plate A (left). Plate B (right).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Manufacturing process

The peel ply technique used to extract sub-laminates from a thick laminate plate was successfully applied in plate A and plate B. However, due to the fact that nylon peel ply has no release coating it

was extremely difficult to separate plate A into sub-laminates. On the contrary the PTFE peel ply of plate B showed excellent releasing characteristics, requiring almost no mechanical effort to separate the sub-laminates.

The fibre content and glass transition temperature of the sub-laminates were measured. While plate A showed fibre weight ratios of 70%, fibre weight ratios of plate B were 5% larger. Void content was below 0.1% and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) glass transition temperatures (T_g) were around 80-85°C. Figure 7 shows that fibre weight ratios and glass transition temperatures through the thickness did not show strong relations with the thickness position.

Plate A and B curing processes were monitored via embedded strain gauges and thermocouples. Figure 5 (left) shows the evolution of the strains during the curing cycle. Three of the four strain gauges showed a minimum peak around 5 hours that corresponds to contraction due to the hardening of the resin. Later, the strains described a monotonic increase driven by the rise in temperature, due to the exothermic curing reaction of the resin, until it settled down during soak two. Finally, when soak two ended the laminate cooled down. The final strain gauges values, are related to the residual stresses that can be found at each thickness position. Residual strain values varied between 40 to 100 micro strains (0.004 to 0.01% elongations) showing no correlation with the thickness position.

Figure 5 (right) and figure 6 (left) show the temperature evolution of the embedded thermocouples for plate A and B. Both show a similar behaviour with maximum temperatures between 80°C and 100°C. In order to avoid excessive temperatures in the middle section of the laminate, soak 1 was setup at a low temperature of 35°C and given enough time to allow some cooling once the exothermic reaction has finished. The signals of the thermocouples showed that higher temperatures occurred in the laminate middle and that the use of soak 1 is necessary in order to avoid temperatures above the post-curing temperature (soak 2).

Strong temperature gradients through the thickness were observed between the top part of the laminate and the mould side. Figure 6 (right) shows the temperature profile through the thickness at the peak temperature time ($t=4.6$ hours). A temperature difference of up to 35°C was observed between the layers close to the mould and the middle layers. Therefore, in view of the strong temperature gradients that appeared through the thickness during the curing process it seems difficult to state which is the curing cycle of a thick laminate. In reality, each layer was following its own curing cycle. The temperature measurements reinforce the hypothesis that mechanical properties in thick laminates vary through the thickness.

3.2 Static tests

Static tests of plate A and B sub-laminates were carried out in order to study the in-plane lamina properties through the thickness. In figure 8 the ultimate stress levels in compression and tension of the sub-laminates are shown. The ultimate stresses offset between plate A and B are related with the 5% fibre weight ratio variation between plate A and B. While the tension tests (see figure 8 right) did not show statistically significant ultimate strengths variations with the thickness position, compression tests ultimate strengths from plate A and B showed a found variation with the thickness position (see figure 8 left), where lower ultimate stresses are located at the outer sides of the thickness and higher ultimate stresses in the middle sections.

Since UD tension ultimate stresses are mainly dominated by the fibre, and UD compression ultimate stresses are influenced by the fibre and matrix resin, it is suspected that the variation of the curing cycles through the thickness was the main cause of the compression ultimate stress variations.

According to the theory of the weakest link the failure in compression of a thick laminate section can be expected to be dominated by the ultimate stresses of the outer layers which show values up to a 18% lower in comparison with the inner layers for the resin/fibre system tested.

Figure 8: Sub-laminates static compression tests through the thickness (left). Sub-laminates static tension tests through the thickness (right).

Figure 9: Compression S-N curves of different sub-laminates (left). Compression aggregated S-N curve of plate B sub-laminates (right).

Figure 10: S-N curves of different sub-laminates (left). Aggregated S-N curve of plate B sub-laminates (right).

3.3 Fatigue tests

Coupons from the same sub-laminates evaluated in the static tests were also tested in fatigue tests. While fatigue tension S-N curves of the sub-laminates did show a weak dependence on the thickness position (see figure 10 left). Fatigue compression S-N curves showed a strong variation with the

sublaminates thickness position as figure 9 left shows. Compression S-N curves at different thickness positions shows similar scatter, but the trend and slope is dependent on the thickness position. Again the outer sub-laminates show lower performance, with shorter fatigue life than the middle sub-laminates. In a similar manner as in the static tests, the differences follow by the compression S-N curves are suspected to be related with the variation of the curing cycles temperatures through the thickness.

As an attempt to characterize the full laminate thickness, each fatigue sublaminates coupon can be considered representative from a volume fraction randomly located at the full plate thickness. Therefore an aggregated S-N curves can be constructed for a thick plate considering all the coupons of separate sub-laminates as one single S-N curve. Such aggregated S-N curves are shown in figure 9 and figure 10 (right side). While the aggregated tension tests S-N curves show a slightly higher scatter than the individual S-N curves, the aggregated compression tests S-N curves showed a strong increase of the scatter in comparison with the individual curves as well as a reduction of the fatigue life.

In a similar manner as in the static tests, it is suspected that according to the theory of the weakest link the shorter fatigue life shown by the sub-laminates from the outer layers will drive the fatigue life of the full thickness laminate.

3 CONCLUSIONS

A technique to extract sub-laminates from a thick laminate plate was successfully applied for two 60 mm thick plates. The temperatures and strains during the manufacturing process were monitored with embedded thermocouples and strain gauges at different thicknesses positions. Residual strains lower than 150 microstrains were observed. Due to the exothermic curing reaction of the resin, a high variability of temperature through the thickness was also observed during the curing cycles. Maximum temperature differences between thickness positions up to 35-40°C were recorded.

Sub-laminates at different thickness positions were tested at 0° orientations in static and fatigue tests. While static and fatigue tension test did not show a strong dependence with the laminate thickness position. Static and fatigue compression tests did show different mechanical properties between the sub-laminates located at the outer thicknesses positions in comparison with the middle positions sub-laminates. Compression ultimate stresses between the middle and outer sub-laminates showed differences of the 18%. In addition, outer sub-laminates S-N curves showed lower fatigue life than middle sub-laminates.

It is concluded that thick laminates mechanical properties through the thickness are not even but function of the thickness position, and such function is defined by the curing cycle that each lamina experiments.

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